

The Impact of Human Capital Attainments on Productivity Growth: An Empirical Investigation

Author's Details: Rasha Qutb-

Lecturer assistant in economics, faculty of commerce, Damanhur University, Egypt.

Abstract

Productivity growth is the backbone of the economy and the key to a sustained economic growth. The important role of human capital in productivity growth has been widely recognized since the seminal works of Schultz (1961), Becker (1964), Welch (1970) and Mincer (1974). Nelson and Phelps (1966) argued that highly-skilled workers are relatively more productive than low-skilled ones and expected to lead to higher productivity growth. Consequently, in an effort to enhance the education quality to boost the economic and productivity growth, many governments invest more in their "driven-growth" sectors including the education sector to yield productive workforce. On this ground, and through the application of Johansen Co-integration test and Error Correction Methodology (CI/ECM), this paper aims at investigating the role of human capital quality in productivity growth in Egypt over the period (1980- 2014). Results reveal that owing to the "drag" type of the education system and the "over-education" phenomenon besides the brain drain, the highly educated workers negatively impact labor productivity growth. Therefore, more efforts should be carried in order for the resulting "output" of the education system to be productive as thought to be.

Key words: Education quality, labor productivity growth, Johansen Co-integration test, ECM, over-education phenomenon.

JEL Classification: I29, J21, J24.

1. Introduction

Productivity growth is vital for economic and social development in any country as being the prime engine of economic growth (Maurel and Seghir 2013). High productivity levels cause higher individuals' income and higher producers' profits which are reproduced in more savings and extra investments and hence, create more jobs and achieve economic progress as well as social welfare (qutb,2017, p.58).

There are many drivers of productivity growth mainly including technology, health and human capital quality. The important role of human capital in productivity growth is widely recognized in the economic literature since the seminal contributions of Schultz (1961), Becker (1964), Welch (1970) and Mincer (1974).

According to the human capital theory, human capital is vital for productivity growth and is accumulated in two ways: experience and education. Cörvers (1975) discusses four effects of human capital on labor productivity; the worker effect, the allocative effect, the diffusion effect, and the research effect. The first two effects support the significance of human capital on productivity level, whereas the last two effects support the significance of human capital on productivity growth (Cörvers.1975, p.5).

Assuming that the output is produced solely by education factor given the other resources, Welch (1970) clarified that the worker effect or "own productivity" effect refers to the positive marginal labor productivity as a result of education. Therefore, the production possibility curve shifts outward owing to a well-educated labor force.

Next, the allocative effect relates the ability of educated workers to efficiently allocate input factors of production (including education itself) to the production process between alternative uses.

Third, the diffusion effect stressed that highly educated workers are expected to be better than lower-educated ones at implementing new ideas, adapting to technological change and introducing more quickly new production. And that leads to more rapid and successful adoption of innovations and higher productivity growth consequently (Cörvers.1975, p.6; Bartel and Lichtenberg,1987, Fallahi et al.,2011).

Finally, the research effect points the role of high education as an important input factor in research and development (R&D) activities. Because such activities are complex they require intermediate and highly-skilled labor to be carried out.

Accordingly, education is viewed as one of the primary means of developing knowledge and skills and hence improving productivity growth; workers with high skills, knowledge coupled with sound physical and mental health can perform their tasks with efficiency and effectiveness and are able to adapt to new technology faster as compared to low educated workers as well (Bong, 2009; Schaffner, 2013, p.496; Arshad and Malik, 2015, P.37; Qutb, 2016, P.164). due to its importance , governments across the globe exert efforts to improve human capital quality through investing in the education sector.

Egypt is thought to be potentially a human capital - rich country; where more than 50% in its population in the working age category. Thereby paying attention to its education sector, as being a "driven-growth" one, will enhance productivity growth. Following that the Egyptian government has pumped massive investment in the education sector over the past forty six years from 650 million LE in 1970, to 94400 million LE in 2015 (CAMPAS, statistical year book, 2014). Nevertheless, the impact of channels through which education can promote growth is not restricted only to public spending devoted to the education sector; quality of education should be considered.

Thereby government efforts to improve human capital quality via education can be evident in terms of gender parity and get gross enrollment rates (Ministry of Education, 2014). It is admitted that achieving higher enrollments and gender parity rates close to universal rates is a necessary condition for development, but the resulting of the education process in terms of qualified and productive labor adaptive to labor market requirement and capable of promoting growth rates as well is a prerequisite condition¹.

On such a ground, and in order to set proper recommendations to policy makers, this paper explores the impact of human capital attributable to the educational attainment of the workforce on labor productivity growth in Egypt throughout the period (1980-2014), by applying the Johansen Co-integration technique and Vector Error Correction Methodology with a single equation (CI/ECM).

The rest of the paper is organized into seven sections. Section 2 demonstrate the relationship between Human capital, Education and Productivity; Section 3 exhibits a background concerning the human capital series in Egypt, measures of human capital efficiency and The structure of employment as well. Section 4 outlines the literature review; Section 5 displays the theoretical model, section 6 presents data sources and the empirical results and finally section 7 clarifies the summary and conclusion.

2- Human capital, Education and Productivity growth

Loosely speaking, human capital corresponds to any stock of knowledge or characteristics the worker has (either innate or acquired) that contributes to his or her "productivity" (Acemoglu, 2010, p.2). A nation's human capital endowment—the skills and capacities that reside in people and that are put to productive use hence, can be a key determinant of its long term economic success than virtually any other resource. This resource must be invested in and leveraged efficiently in order for it to generate returns—for the individuals involved as well as an economy as a whole (The Human Capital Report 2015,p3). Accordingly, human capital investment does not restricted to education only, rather it captures all investments in individuals that are made to improve their skills, including health, on- the job training, informal education and learning-by-doing or any other deeds that improve the fruitful use of an individual's skills.

In fact the term "Human Capital" is firstly appeared in the writings of Theodore Schultz, as he wrote: "*I propose to treat education as an investment in man. Since education becomes a part of a person receiving it, I shall refer to it as human capital*" (Schultz, 1960). In Schultz's view, an individual's stock of human capital

¹ Although enrolment and attainment measures show exposure to learning, they don't capture the quality of these learning environments and may be incomplete on their own (human capital report, 2015,P. 5).

may be regarded as an asset on which an income or 'return' comparable to rent or interest is earned, hence human capital can be considered as a separate factor of production like physical capital and labor.

Also, Schultz argued that a large share of economic growth comes from further additions to the initial stock of human capital, and that human capital accumulation was largely responsible for the "residual" in early growth accounting exercises (Qutb, 2016,45; Arfooz et al., 2010,47; Goldin, 2014,1; Jones, 1999).

In his article "investment in human capital", Schultz named three characterized economists who have looked on individual as a capital. The first was Adam Smith (1776)² who included all the acquired and useful abilities of all individuals as a part of capital (Schultz,1961,p.2). Also, H. Von Thunen who argued that the concept of man capital does not humiliate his freedom and nobility. And lastly, Irving Fisher (1897) that logically gave a comprehensive concept of capital, and he cited J.S. Nicholson for the term "living capital" as opposed to "dead capital"((Schultz,1961, p.2; Acemoglu, 2010, p.2).

Productivity growth refers to an increase in the value of outputs produced for a given level of inputs, over a given period of time. According to Becker (1964), education or training raises workers productivity by passing on valuable knowledge and skills, hence raising workers' future income by increasing their lifetime earnings. Also, the continuing growth in per capita incomes of many countries during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries is partly due to the expansion of scientific and technical knowledge that raises the productivity of labor and other inputs in production. And the increasing reliance of industry on sophisticated knowledge greatly enhances the value of education, technical schooling, on-the-job training, and other human capital forms (Becker,1975).

On the micro level, Becker (1964) and Mincer (1974) provided explanations that link investment with the training of workers and wages. In particular, the human capital theory draws a crucial distinction between general education and firm-specific training. More skilled or better educated workers can contribute effectively to the acquisition of productive resources and easily adapt new technology and facilitating technological transfer. Becker states in his article "the age of human capital" in 1961 page 5: *"The global economy cannot succeed without considerable investment in human capital by all nations. Richer countries specialize in high-knowledge products and services, while poorer nations specialize in lower-skilled and raw material-intensive products. Still, investments in human capital are also necessary in poorer nations if they are to have a chance of growing out of poverty...In particular, although on the average Third World nations grew a little less rapidly than richer ones, poorer nations with more educated and healthier populations managed to grow faster than average. Especially important for these nations are their investments in elementary and secondary education"*.

At the Micro level, we have at least three different ways in which education can affect productivity; the theory of human capital, the "signaling" model of education and the environment in which labor acts.

First, according to *the theory of human capital*, Becker (1975) argues that education teaches workers valuable skills which make them more productive. Given their higher productivity, more educated workers earn higher wages. To choose the optimal level of education, workers compare the present value of lifetime earnings associated with different levels of schooling. They remain in school as long as the marginal benefits of schooling outweigh the marginal costs.

Second, *the "signaling" or "sorting" model of education* argues that more educated workers receive higher wages, not necessarily because school has taught them any valuable skills, but because firms use education as an informational signal to differentiate high-quality workers from low-quality workers. Underlying this theory is the idea that a worker's educational attainment is correlated with other unobserved characteristics that existed before he made his schooling decision. Therefore the "signaling" theory overstates the impact of education on productivity (Weiss, 1995, p.134).

Third, it is possible that all workers with the same level of schooling do not have the same productivity due to differences in their environment which affect the productivity-enhancing effects of education. According to this school of thought, the returns to schooling are higher in dynamic environments because education improves

² In his fourth definition of capital Smith (1776) noted: "The acquisition of ... talents during ... education, study, or apprenticeship, costs a real expense, which is capital in [a] person. Those talents [are] part of his fortune [and] likewise that of society"

workers' access to information (Thomas et al., 1991) and their ability to interpret and understand new information. In that context, Nelson and Phelps (1966) argue that the marginal productivity of education is an increasing function of the rate of technological innovation (Nelson and Phelps, 1966; Schultz, 1975) In addition, the demand for skills is assumed to rise during periods of technological change because of the comparative advantage that educated workers have in implementing new technology (Bartel and Lichtenberg, 1987; Rosenzweig, 1995, Acemoglu, 2010,14:226).

3. Background

Human capital is critical not only to the productivity of society but also the functioning of its political, social and civic institutions hence; understanding its current state and capacity is valuable. In such a respect, in this section we are going to distinguish between three perceptions of human capital then examine two measures of its efficiency in an economy. Lastly, we will take a closer look at the size of human capital stock that can potentially be deployed in the labor market and the extent it is actually deployed in workforce that help analyze how well it is being utilized and the extent it has contributed to the labor productivity growth over the past 35 years.

3.1 Human capital series in Egypt

We can differentiate between three concepts of human capital:

(1) Potential stock of human capital

It refers to the human capital embedded in our population aged above 15 years. As indicated in figure (1), the potential stock of human capital stock has an increasing trend throughout the period (1976-2015) constituting on average about 54.5% of total population size. Actually, this is a favoring percentage for economic growth and development, only if it is utilized in an optimum way.

Also, the available data on table (1) revealed that over the last 40 years, Egypt's potential stock of human capital has grown by 233%; from 17.9 to about 60.5 million individuals, which is much faster than the head count population growth of 148% (from 45.1 million in year 1976 to 91 million individuals in year 2015).

Figure (1) Human capital stock embedded in population aged 15+ VS. Total population

(2) Utilized portion of potential human capital stock

It covers only those workers who are in the workforce (Human capital stock in labor force). Whereas the non-active portion corresponds to that part of the human capital stock for economically inactive people who choose to stay out of the workforce, e.g. full-time student that aged 15+, non-working housewives, and retirees.

Figure (2) Human capital stock in labor force VS. Human capital stock embedded in population aged 15+

(3) *Human capital stock in employment*

It denotes labor force that is deployed or utilized, and captures around 91% on average of the active part of potential human capital, and 49% of total potential human capital stock in Egypt throughout the period (1976-2015).

Figure (3): Total employment versus Human capital stock in labor force and Human capital stock embedded in population aged 15+

3.2 *Is human capital in Egypt actively in use?*

In order to know to what extent the effective human capital is being utilized, we have two measures:

a. *The human capital stock utilization rate (u)*

It refers to the extent to which the human capital in the population is economically active and measure “How much of the economy’s human capital stock is actually utilized?”, and can be calculated as follows:

$$u = (HK_L / HK_P) * 100$$

the human capital stock utilization rate (u) is get by the ratio of the active portion of human capital stock embedded in the labor force (K_L) to that of total potential human capital stock in the working age population (K_P). **Table (1) the evolution of total population and human capital stock series in Egypt**

During the period (1976-2015)

item	1976	1986	1996	2003	2006	2010	2015
Population size (in million person)	45.1	51.8	63.6	72.2	76.3	82	91
The potential human capital (Population above 15 years)	17.99	22.720	28.979	32.766	45.815	50.650	60.554
*Active portion of potential human capital (Labor force in million)	9	12.774	19.925	20	23.2	26.2	28.4
*Employment (million)	8	11.9806	15.4	18.1	20.4	23.8	24.8
*Human capital utilization rate	50%	56.2%	68.8%	61.0%	50.6%	51.7%	46.9%
*Employment rate	88.8%	93.7%	77.3%	90.5%	88%	90.8%	87.3%

Source: CAMPAS, statistical book year. *Researcher's calculation.

It is noticed from data in table (1) that overall the period (1976-2015), human capital utilization rate gets 53% on average owing to people with high education stop working or retire early. Also, the human capital utilization rate is relatively low and starts apparently to deteriorate after year 2003 and reaches its minimum rate 47% in year 2015 representing a “loss” in human capital which can otherwise be deployed.

a. *The employment rate of human capital (e)*

Another measure of the human capital efficiency that is economically used is “the employment rate” of human capital. It refers to the extent to which the human capital among the economically active workers is actually deployed in the production process, and calculated as follows:

$$e = (K_E / K_L) * 100$$

The employment rate is the ratio of total employment (K_E) to the active portion of human capital stock embedded in the labor force (K_L). The available data in table (1) shows that the real employment rate in the Egyptian economy represents on average 89.5% out of the total active portion of human capital and has constituted around 48.4% on average of the potential human capital in the Egyptian economy since the adoption of the open door policy in the late 1974.

3.3 *The structure of employment in Egypt*

By taking a closer look to the structure of employment in the Egyptian labor market during the period from 1980 to 2015, as indicated by table (2), we notice the following:

(a) The demand for unskilled / illiterate labor was dominating the Egyptian labor market till year 1997, afterwards it starts to decline but still the contribution of that working category is higher than that of skilled workers in the labor market till now.

With reference to its share out of the workforce, it is noticed that it has declined over the period of study, on average, from 61% during the 80s to 44% throughout the 90s and to 31% during the last three years. Although these figures reflects upgrading in the construction of workforce, it needs more attention and extra cutback efforts; because illiteracy represents a direct threat to both social and economic stability in any country; as it restrains achieving a sustainable economic growth which denotes a hindrance to poverty rates reduction, also it reflects deterioration in the stock of human capital (Qutb, 2016, 169).

(b) The intermediate skilled labor; those with education degree up to secondary level, has enjoyed a dominant share in the Egyptian workforce since 1998 till 2015; where their share has been amplified over the period from 30% during the 80s, reached 34.7% throughout the 90s, and has gone to 45% during the last three years. This is a reasonable fact since Egypt is a lower middle income country that is driven broadly by manufacturing and agriculture sectors. These sectors primarily demand semi-skilled labor to handle machines and less complex technical chores. An adoption of advanced technology could simply increase productivity and moving toward a knowledge-based economy will help absorb the appropriate qualifications³.

³ A knowledge economy is one in which knowledge is acquired, created, disseminated, and used effectively as the key engine of economic growth and accordingly enhance economic development. (World Bank Institute, 2007) Contrary to some beliefs, the concept of the knowledge economy does not necessarily revolve around high technology or information technology (IT). (World Bank Institute, 2007) A “Knowledge Society” however, refers to the type of society that is needed to compete and succeed in the changing economic and political dynamics of the modern world. It refers to societies that are well educated, and who therefore rely on the knowledge of their citizens to drive the innovation, entrepreneurship and dynamism of that society’s economy. A knowledge-based economy is characterized by high investment in R&D, high literacy, high tertiary education enrolments, good technology-related capacity and skills, strength in innovation, and high ICT penetration and internet usage (El-Tanany, 2013, 15).

(c) Concerning the skilled labor; those with tertiary education; their contribution out of workforce has enlarged from 8.7% on average during 80s, reached 21.2% in the 90s, and gone to 24% throughout the last three years.

**Table (2) the evolution of enrollment rates and employment in Egypt
Over the period (1980-2015)**

item	1980	1986	1990	1996	1997	1998	2003	2006	2010	2015
Employment (million)	8	11.98	13.5	15.4	15.8	16.2	18.1	20.4	23.8	24.8
Illiterate workers (%)	63.0%	62.1%	59.3%	43.4%	40.8%	37.4%	32.1%	33.3%	29.5%	29%
Workers with secondary education %	26.8%	32.7%	25.8%	34.7%	37.2%	40.4%	41.7%	43.8%	47.0%	48.4%
Workers with tertiary education (%)	10.2%	5.2%	14.9%	22.0%	22%	22.2%	26.2%	22.9%	23.5%	22.6%

Source: CAMPAS, statistical book year.

In fact, the Egyptian economy is far from being a knowledge – based one; as the ICT sector contributes to only 2.3 % of its GDP (world bank, Knowledge assessment methodology (KAM), cited in Arab knowledge report 2009, p.209) so it is reasonable for the highly educated workers to constitute a lower portion in labor market and unemployment rate is the largest among the universities graduates. With so few opportunities for graduates and so little money for research, it is of no surprise that Egypt has lost so many scientists abroad, especially in engineering and IT.

4. Literature review

In general, studies on the impact of human capital quality on productivity growth include both health and education aspects and divided into a cross-countries study and country specific study. Concerning education impact, which is the main target of this study; variables commonly used as proxies for education quality are literacy rate, mean years of schooling, educational level of workforce, and school enrollment rate and government expenditure on education.

Concerning the relationship between education quality, measured by workforce's education levels, and productivity growth, it has found much attention of economists and researchers but the previous empirical evidence is mixed. For instance, Belorgey et al., (2004) had investigated determinants of Productivity per Employee using year 2000 dataset. They focused on the role of human capital, public infrastructure, financial development, information and communications technology (ICT) spending and unemployment rate for two samples of countries and applied the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) method in their estimations. Two different approaches are used to study labor productivity: The determinants of its growth rate are estimated across a panel of 25 industrialized countries using the generalized method of moments (GMM) in the 1990s are first examined, and then The determinants of productivity levels are estimated using GDP in purchasing power parity (PPP) per employee in 2000 in a 77-country sample, using a more structural approach. Additionally a sub-sample of 49 countries is used to capture the impact on productivity of spending on information and communication technologies. the findings revealed that human capital (measured by gross school enrollment in secondary and tertiary education) was positively significant as a determinant of labor productivity in both samples. In Tanzania, Goedhuys et al (2008) found that human capital quality has insignificant impact on labor productivity in the manufacturing sector (except the CEO'S education level). Ismail (2009) attempts to analyze the impact of human capital attainment among workers for the Malay owned manufacturing and services enterprises on output and labor productivity. The analysis is based on 574 Malay firms surveyed in 2001/2002, which covers 264 manufacturing enterprises and 310 services enterprises in Peninsular Malaysia. The output and labor productivity of the firms are regressed against the human capital variables like education and training together with physical capital stock. The study shows that for the manufacturing enterprises, an effective labor plays a higher and significant role on output and labor productivity growth. Also the capital- labor ratio is an important determinant of labor productivity. Decker et al.(2009) utilized Carlino and Voith's (1992) model of state labor productivity, which proxies labor productivity using real per worker wages, to examine data from the 1989 to 2000 period, with particular emphasis on the late 1990s, a period when labor productivity boomed

throughout the nation. They estimate how state characteristics such as population density, education (measured by the population above 25 years with university degree and above), industrial structure, and business amenities (such as crime rates), influence state labor productivity in U.S. by using CES production function. The model was estimated over two sub-periods (1989 to 1995 and 1996 to 2000) in order to isolate the labor productivity boom of the late 1990s. The determinants of labor productivity changed during the productivity boom of the late 1990s. During the period 1996 to 2000 greater industrial diversity appeared to have stimulated labor productivity, whereas in the earlier period, 1989 to 1995, specialization and education appear to have significant impact on labor productivity growth.

Ajri and Ismail (2010) attempt to observe to what extent the Malaysian economy has benefited from educational expansion over the period (1981-2007). The production and productivity functions are estimated using the quality of labor together with the capital stock as independent variables. The effective labor and the level of education obtained by the employment are used as indicators to measure quality of labor. The study reveals that the capital stock and capital-labor ratio played a major role in contributing to the Malaysian economic growth and labor productivity respectively. The effective labor did play a positive role in determining economic growth but its contribution is less than the physical labor. The authors suggest that the education system must be geared towards producing workforce that can efficiently be used in the labor market.

Fallahi et al.,(2011) investigate the determinants of labor productivity at the firm level in the Iran's manufacturing sector with an emphasis on education and training levels provided by the enterprise to the employees.. The analysis is based on descriptive statistics and cross sectional regression models on a sample of 12299 Industrial firms in the year 2007. The results show that labor productivity is positively related to real wage, fixed capital per employee, export orientation, R&D activity and the educational level of labor force. While the education of work force has a significant positive effect on labor productivity, the effect of firm training expenditures was significant and negative. This demonstrates the inefficacy of trainings within the enterprise in comparison to trainings that they get before being hired. Based on this result the study emphasized on the importance of increasing educational level of work force in Iran also, trainings within firms should be skill increasing and coordinated with the job needs of individuals.in addition, the Positive effect of research and development costs on productivity highlights the need to pay more attention to creating and strengthening R&D units in firms.

Abdul Rehman and Mughal (2013) analyze the influence of skilled labor and unskilled labor upon the labor productivity of over the period (1990-2011) in Pakistan. After applying the linear Regression upon The Cobb Douglas Production Function, findings showed that the skilled labor has a positive impact on labor productivity and the unskilled labor has a negative impact on the Labor Productivity; if the skilled labor increases 1% then the labor productivity Increases by 43.6% and if the unskilled labor increases 1% then the labor productivity decreases by 70.6%. Based on the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) method of estimation,

More recently, In Malaysia, both Arshada and Malika (2015) investigate the impacts of human capital on labor productivity in 14 states in Malaysia using panel data analysis over the period (2009-2012). Human capital variables are represented by educational levels and health status. by using the fixed effects generalized least squares (GLS) model, the results show that human capital quality (higher educational levels and better health status) is positively significant in improving the level of labor productivity in Malaysia. Therefore Improvements in the quality of health and education are therefore crucial for Malaysia to achieve higher productivity growth but the impact of health on labor productivity is greater than the impact of education. Also, the magnitude of secondary education is significantly higher than the effects of tertiary education because the Malaysian economy remains a middle-income economy, driven broadly by manufacturing, construction and mining sectors. These sectors primarily rely on workers with secondary education to handle machines and less complex technical chores. An adoption of advanced technology could simply increase productivity.

A survey of the literature reveals that there is a much degree of consensus about the positive impacts of education quality on productivity growth due to several factors including: enabling workers to yield a valuable work and in addition they increase the productivity of other factors of production. Also, education assists in carrying out the invention; exploration and innovation. Furthermore, it helps educated people to create major

developments at industrial countries with the optimal allocation of scarce resources (Tabari and Reza, 2012, p.1266).

5. Theoretical model

Referring to the economic literature and the previous empirical studies that estimate the impact of workforce composition, as a proxy for skills and human capital quality, on labor productivity growth the functional form of the proposed model can be written as follow⁴:

$$LP_t = F(Ho_t, HE_t, PREH_t, RAW_t)$$

The productivity growth/ the dependent variable (LP_t) is represented by the value added per worker multiplied by working hours. The explanatory variables include human capital input represented by the low, intermediate and highly-skilled workers in the whole economy and average real wages.

Here workers are categorized according to their education level into low-skilled workers /illiterates (Ho_t), intermediate- skilled workers/ with pre higher education degree ($PREH_t$), and highly- skilled workers/with tertiary education (HE_t). Real average wages $Ln RAW$ are get by dividing real annual wages by the number of labor.

Firstly, the augmented Dickey- Fuller (ADF) unit root test is conducted on the time series macro-variables in the study to avoid "spurious regression". And in-order to establish a long run-relationship between the variables, Johansen's Co-integration test is employed. Finally, to combine the long-run and the short-run dynamics Error-Correction Model (with a single equation) is used where the final structural form is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} Ln LP_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta Ln LP_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \Delta Ln HO_{(t-1)} + \beta_3 \Delta Ln PREH_{(t-1)} + \beta_4 \Delta HE_{(t-1)} \\ & + \beta_5 Ln RAW_{(t-1)} + \lambda (Ln LP_{(t-1)} - \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 Ln HO_{(t-1)} - \alpha_2 Ln PREH_{(t-1)} \\ & - \alpha_3 HE_{(t-1)} - \alpha_4 Ln RAW_{(t-1)} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Note that all terms in equation above are $I(0)$ as long as the "α" coefficients (the "co-integrating vector") are known or at least consistently estimated. The term is the magnitude by which "y" was above or below its long-run equilibrium value in the previous period. The coefficient λ (which we expect to be negative) represents the amount of "correction" of this period ($t - 1$) disequilibrium that happens in period t . The following hypothesis is established:

Ho: There is no significant long run relationship between education quality, average wages and Productivity growth.

H1: There is a significant long run relationship between education quality, annual average wages and Productivity growth.

6. Data sources and empirical results

6.1 Data sources

The empirical investigation has been carried out in the case on Egyptian economy with a dataset of the period 1980 to 2014. The present study uses data which have been collected from the planning ministry, ministry of education, and CAMPAS, (<http://www.CAMPAS.gov.eg>). The reliability of the data for empirical research can be attributed to the fact that all the data sources used in this study are government sources, and thus data is very much reliable for policy research. The data variables used in the present study are: gross domestic product, the annual working hours, total labor size, the classification of the workforce size according to their

⁴ There are many factors that enhance labor productivity not included in the study due to limited data availability such as research and development data and training.

education level (proxy for skills), and real annual wage. All data used are expressed in constant prices in order to avoid the inflation effect. Statistical description of the relationship is described in the following sub-section.

6.2 Empirical results

6.2.1 Unit root test.

Before examining the Johansen's co-integration technique, all the variables are to be tested for stationary as a prerequisite. The results of the Augmented Dickey- Fuller (ADF) unit root test as shown in table 3 revealed that all the variables under study are stationary at the first differences (integrated of order one in its level at 5% level).

Table 3: Stationarity of the Time Series using ADF test

variables	ADF (t- statistic)	Critical value (1%)	(5%) level	(10%) level	Probability*	Degree of co-integration (at level)
LnLP1	-7.029	-2.6	-1.9	-1.6	0.000	I(1)
Ln H0	-4.41	-2.6	-1.9	-1.6	0.0001	I(1)
Ln PREH	-1.7	-2.6	-1.9	-1.6	0.07	I(1)
HE	-3.45	-3.6	-2.95	-2.61	0.0159	I(1)
LnRAW	-4.09	-2.67	-1.95	-1.6	0.000	I(1)

Source: computed by using E-Views packages

Once the series are made stationary, they can be used in regression analysis. But the drawback of this method is the possibility of losing long-run information about the variables. This problem can be overcome by applying the Johansen co-integration technique, which shows the long-run equilibrium relationship between two or more non-stationary series.

6.2.2 Johansen Co integration test

The variables are said to be co-integrated if they are integrated of order one. To find out the number of co-integrating vectors we have applied maximum likelihood-based λ -max and λ -trace statistics introduced by (Johansen, 1988; 1992) and (Johansen and Juselius, 1990). In a set of m series, if there are 'r' co integrating vectors, then there are (m-r) common stochastic trends. By applying Johansen co-integration test for the variables of the study, the results exhibit the existence of long run equilibrium relationship between variables according to the values of Trace statistics and Max-Eigen (which test the null hypothesis that the number of co-integrated variables less than or equal r) hence we cannot reject the hypothesis of existing at least one co-integrated vector between the variables.

Table (4): Johansen Co-integration Test for the model of labor productivity growth determinants

a) Concerning the value of Trace statistics

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace	5% Critical Value	Prob.**	Result
None *(r=0)	0.668815	77.73641	69.81889	0.0102	Reject H ₀
At most 1 *(r<=1)	0.429454	41.26884	47.85613	0.1803	Accept H ₀
At most 2 *(r<=2)	0.245772	22.75054	29.79707	0.2585	Accept H ₀
At most 3 *(r<=3)	0.216775	13.44254	15.49471	0.0996	Accept H ₀

Trace test indicates 1 co-integrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level.

b) Concerning the value of max-Eigen

(Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue))

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob.**	Result
None *(r=0)	0.668815	36.46756	33.87687	0.0240	Reject H0
At most 1 *(r<=1)	0.429454	18.51831	27.58434	0.4526	Accept H0
At most 2 *(r<=2)	0.245772	9.307995	21.13162	0.8068	Accept H0
At most 3 *(r<=3)	0.216775	8.063073	14.26460	0.3723	Accept H0

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 co-integrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level.

*denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Source: computed by using E-Views packages.

The trace test statistics indicates one co-integration equation at 5% level assuming three lag in the test equation. Therefore, Co-integration indicates the presence of a linear combination of non-stationary variables that are stationary. This means that the time series of the variables are stationary and are related with each other in the long run, and they have to be included in error correction model⁵.

6.2.3 Error Correction Model

The ECM result of the model of estimating the impact of education quality on labor productivity growth is presented in the table (5). And the estimated model in long run can be written as follows:

$$\ln LP_t = -4.19 - 0.205 \ln HO_t + 0.46 \ln PREH_t - 0.03 HE_t - 0.08 \ln RAW_t$$

(0.03632) (0.04797) (0.01442) (0.03189)

The empirical results indicate that the estimated long run effect of a 10% increase in intermediate-skilled workers causes about 4.6% increase in labor productivity growth, keeping other variables constant. On the other hand, the long run impact of both skilled/ highly educated workers and unskilled/ illiterate ones is negative. Around 10% increase in illiterate workers entrance in labor market cause a reduction in labor productivity growth by 2%. Similarly, the increase in the number of highly educated workers by million workers will cause a reduction in labor productivity growth by 0.03% in the long run.

The feeble impact of highly - educated workers on labor productivity growth can be addressed in the context of the following:

First: "the over-educated" phenomenon⁶; as really the economy does not need this massive numbers of accountants, lawyers and historians that exceed what is the labor market need hence unemployment is a logic consequence. Those unemployed people have many options; either stay unemployed for even more and more time, or accept to work in jobs don't relate to their qualification, or even below their qualifications, or below their income expectation limit and their social status. All of these factors represent a "loss" in human capital and hence contribute to lower labor productivity growth and consequently slow down the economic growth rates. We should declare that the over-educated phenomenon is due to the "drag" education system

⁵ Where the short-run dynamics of the variables in the ECM are represented by the series in differences and the long-run relationships by the variables in levels

⁶ For more information about this phenomenon see: -Machlup, F., (1982), "Issues in the Theory of Human Capital: Education as Investment" The Pakistan Development Review, Vol. XXI, No.1, pp1:17. And; Lewis, W. Arthur. "Education and Economic Development". Social and Economic Studies (Jamaica). Vol. 10. 1961. (Reprinted in Mary Jean Bowman et al. (eds.), Readings in the Economics of Education. Paris: UNESCO.1968

Second: The *weak external efficiency* of public education's spending policy in Egypt⁷; its symptoms include deterioration in the education quality in most public scholastic institutions⁸.

Third: the *wrong educational mix*; or the mismatch between labor market requirement and graduates qualifications is also responsible to a degree; where most students choose to specialize in the theoretical areas rather than practical ones that labor market really needs. a reasonable result of this wrong educational mix is the persistent unemployment of highly educated people.

Fourth: *Brain drain*; which can be categorized into external and internal brain drain. The former refers to the so the international migration of high-level educated workers from developing to developed countries (Todaro,1990,p.384), and that constitutes a major challenge for Egypt in building knowledge economy since the human capital is the most significant building block of the knowledge economy. Egypt scored (2.1) on the Human Capital Flight Index 2009, which measures the extent to which Egypt loses its "Knowledge Workers" abroad on a scale of (1-7). (Bond, Maram, Soliman, & Khattab, 2012, Al Tanany,2013, p.75).

On the other hand, the internal / Intellectual brain drain refers to the transfer of thoughts about the issues concerns of developing nations related to urgent issues such as health, education, unemployment and rural development to issues more suit the developed country' stage of development.

Table (5): long run relationship of the variables estimated using ECM

Co integrating Eq:	CointEq1
LNLP1(-1)	1.000000
LNHo(-1)	0.205368 (0.03632) [5.65444]
LNPRESH(-1)	-0.461205 (0.04797) [-9.61437]
HE(-1)	0.033309 (0.01442) [2.30925]
LNRAW(-1)	0.085282 (0.03189) [2.67413]
C	4.195668

Source: computed by using E-Views packages.
Values in brackets: Standard Error

Also, the estimated results evident that labor productivity growth appears to be negatively affected by real average wages in the long run are conflicting with "wage efficiency" model⁹ owing to many reasons such as:

- a. The wage rate doesn't reflect the real marginal productivity of labor due to the distortion in the input factors market;

⁷ The concept of efficiency generally describes how available resources are used to achieve desired outcomes. External efficiency is refereed by the relation between input and output of the education system. this helps in justifying the investment in education based on the higher social rate of return than other alternatives (Qutb,2016,p.168)

⁸ For more details about the external efficiency of the pubic subsidization policy in Egypt see: Qutb, R. 2016. Analyzing the External and Internal Efficiency Considerations in Public Subsidization of Education in Egypt. Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development, Vol 7, No 12, pp. 164-172.

⁹ According to wage-efficiency model, the wage rate above the market clearing level will increase labor productivity. And this could be explained in terms of two models; "Incentives-driven model" known as "Shirking model" states that as wage level increases, labor force will be more driven to keep their jobs and will therefore try to increase their productivity level to avoid being fired. The "gift exchange" model is based on the assumption that high wages change the relationship between employer and employee. Employee will be more attached to employer and try to increase his own productivity (Fallahi, 2011,172).

- b. The law of minimum wage rate hasn't been yet set in motion, besides, the overlooking of equal distribution of wages among workers with equal educated level across sectors; therefore and due to such an imbalance the increase in wages doesn't necessary lead to productivity growth.
- c. As indicated by (Taylor and Walters,1977; Hirsch and Hausman,1983), in some situations the rise in wage rate drives workers to reduce their working hours and call for more leisure time.

After estimating the long-run relationship among the variables, we can then go ahead to estimate the short-run relationships of the variables. The estimated coefficients of the model show the immediate and the lagged impact of (dlnHo_t), (d HE_t), (dLn PREH_t), and (dLn RAW_t) on (dlnlp_t) that can be written as follows:

$$\Delta Ln LP_t = \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 \Delta Ln HO_{(t-1)} + \alpha_2 \Delta Ln HO_{(t-1)} + \alpha_3 \Delta Ln RAW_{(t-i)} + \lambda EC_{(t-i)} + u_t$$

$$= 0.02 - 0.62 \Delta Ln HO_{t-1} + 0.5 \Delta Ln RAW_{t-1} - 0.67 EC_{t-i}$$

(0.02) (0.18) (0.17) (0.28)

The estimated value " co-integrating vector estimates", λ= (-0.67), represents the rate of adjustment speed of short run labor productivity growth towards its equilibrium level in the long run (on average); which means that around 67% of previous deviation of actual labor productivity growth (t-1), from its equilibrium value will be corrected in the time period (because the sign is negative). Thus, it needs around 1.5 year for labor productivity growth to return to its equilibrium.

While in short run there is no evidence of the positive impact of education quality (neither indicated by secondary education nor highly education) on labor productivity growth. On the other hand, the increase in the employment of illiterate workers by 1% cause a reduction in labor productivity growth by 0.6% for one lagged period. Despite of having a negative impact on labor productivity growth in the long run, the average real wage appears to positively affect the labor productivity growth in the short run with one lagged period.

Finally and returning back to our main question "Does education at all levels matter for productivity growth?" the answer, in the case of Egypt, is no, due to the "drag" type of the education system .hence, more efforts should be carried on a basis of analysis and research in order for the resulting of the education system to be productive as thought to be.

Table (4): The short run relationship of the variables estimated using VECM

Error Correction:	D(LNLP1)
CointEq1	-0.67 (0.28) [-2.39]
D(LNHI(-1))	-0.616185 (0.18448) [-3.34017]
D(LNHI(-2))	0.465794 (0.18633) [2.49985]
D(LNRAW(-1))	0.500980 (0.17734) [2.82495]
C	0.021023 (0.02537) [0.82851]
R-squared	0.719838
Adj. R-squared	0.565749
Sum sq. resids	0.059712
S.E. equation	0.054641
F-statistic	4.671574
Log likelihood	55.13722
Akaike AIC	-2.696076
Schwarz SC	-2.146425

Source: computed by using E-Views packages

7. Conclusion.

Productivity growth refers to an increase in the value of outputs produced for a given level of inputs, over a given period of time. And it is vital for economic and social development in any country, thereby constitutes the prime engine of economic growth (Maurel and Seghir 2013). The issue of improving productivity growth is well stressed in developing and less developing countries that confront a stern deterioration in its economic and social conditions owing to the misuse of the available human and physical resources (Qutb, 2016, P.58, El Feil, 2006). There is a wide census, both theoretically and empirically, about the role of education as one of the main drivers of productivity growth; given that it is a well-planned one with a high quality that suits labor market requirements and is adaptive to "development process" agenda of the country. Accordingly, many economies try to boost its economy by investing more in its "driven- growth" sectors such as education one, in an effort to increase the education quality. But quality can't be easily gained by just throwing money in the sector; while observing the market needs and working on the requirements of the phase of country's development process is of priority. Also, analyzing the human capital attainments, the product of the education process, and its impact on productivity growth is badly urgent in order to know whether we are walking on the right development track or we mislead the right way. On this ground, this paper analyzes the impact of human capital attainment among workers on productivity growth in Egypt throughout the period (1980-2014) to answer the question "are highly educated workers truly productive?", and through applying Johansen Co-integration test and Vector Error Correction Methodology with single equation, the answer is no; findings indicate that labor productivity growth is stimulated by workers with education degree up to secondary level, while it is negatively affected by those with universities degree and above. This is due to the "drag" type of the education system and "the over-educated" phenomenon and its reasonable result is the persistent unemployment. This represents a "loss" in human capital and contributes to lower labor productivity growth and consequently slow down the economic growth rates. Hence, achieving higher enrollments and gender parity rates close to universal rates is not enough condition to achieve productivity and economic growth, while the output of the education process in terms of productive labor adaptive to labor market requirement is a sufficient condition. Also, although increasing the education budget could help to overcome many of the current deficiencies that exist in the system including: Poor quality of educational inputs and processes; Limited access to educational opportunities especially in the poor and deprived areas, quality control is of importance to guarantee achieving the objective of the education system. Therefore, more efforts should be carried on a basis of analysis and research in order for the resulting of the education system to be productive as thought to be.

References

- i. Abdul Rehman, R. and Mughal, KH. 2013. *Impact of Technical Education on the Labor Productivity. International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management. VOL. 2, NO. 7, PP. 2307-2466.*
- ii. Acemoglu, D. 2010. *Lecture Notes for Graduate Labor Economics. Vol 14, issue 662, PP.1-289.*
- iii. Ajri, I. and Ismail, R. 2010. *Impact of labour quality on labour productivity and economic growth. African Journal of Business Management, Vol. 4, NO 4. pp. 486-495.*
- iv. Al Tanany, S.M. 2013. *"Moving towards a knowledge- based economy: What is needed to enable science, technology and innovation in post- revolutionary Egypt", A Master thesis in public administration, The American University in Cairo, School of Global Affairs and Public Policy, pp:1-131.*
- v. Arfooz, A. Abdul Rahim, KH. Noor,Z. and Chin, L. 2010. *Human Capital and Labor Productivity in Food Industries of Iran. International Journal of Economics and Finance, Vol. 2, No. 4, PP 47:51.*
- vi. Arshada, M. and Malika, Z. 2015. *Quality Of Human Capital And Labor Productivity: A Case Of Malaysia. International Journal of Economics Management and Accounting, Vol 23, no. 1, pp. 37-55.*
 - a. Available at: <http://subnet.loginto.me/lecture-notes-on-labor-economics-cerge-ei.pdf>
 - b. Available at: www.worldresearchlibrary.org.
 - c. Available online at [//www.pelagiaresearchlibrary.com](http://www.pelagiaresearchlibrary.com).
- vii. Becker, G. 1961. *The age of human capital, PP1-6.*

- viii. Belorgey, N. Lecat, R. and Maury, T. 2004. *Determinants of Productivity per Employee: an Empirical Estimation Using Panel Data*. Banque DE France working paper, NO 110, PP.1-46.
- ix. Covers, F. 1997. *The Impact of human capital on labor productivity in manufacturing sectors of the European union*. *Applied Economics*, vol29, issue8, pp. 975-987
- x. Decker, C. Thompson, E. and Wohar, M. 2009. *Determinants of State Labor Productivity: The Changing Role of Density*. *The journal of regional analysis and policy*, Vol 39, no 1, pp1:10.
- xi. El Feil, O. 2006. *The relation between wages and productivity in the transformation industries in Egypt: an empirical and analytical study in the context of ERSAP*. PhD thesis, faculty of commerce, Alexandria University.
- xii. Fallahi, F. Sojoodi, S. Mehin, S. Aslaninia, E. 2011. *The determinants of labour productivity in Iran's manufacturing firms: an emphasis on labour education and training*. *International Conference on Applied Economics*, pp. 169-177.
- xiii. Goedhuys, M. Janz, N. and Mohnen, P. 2008. *What drives productivity in Tanzanian manufacturing firms: technology or business environment?* *The European Journal of Development Research*, Vol 20, issue 2, pp. 199–218. doi:10.1080/09578810802060785
- xiv. Goldin, C. 2014. *Human Capital*. *Handbook of Cliometrics*, Claude Diebolt and Michael Hauptert, editors Springer-Verlag,
- xv. http://media.hoover.org/sites/default/files/documents/0817928928_3.pdf
- xvi. Ismail, R. 2009. *The Impact of Human Capital Attainment on Output and Labor Productivity of Malay Firms*. *The Journal of International Management Studies*, Volume 4, Number 1, PP. 221-230.
- xvii. Jones, J. 1999. *Are Educated Really Workers More Productive?*. Department of Economics, Vassar College.
- xviii. -Lewis, W. Arthur. 1961. *Education and Economic Development*. *Social and Economic Studies (Jamaica)*. Vol. 10.
- xix. Machlup, F. 1982. *Issues in the Theory of Human Capital: Education as Investment*. *The Pakistan Development Review*, Vol. XXI, No.1, pp1:17.
- xx. Maurel, M. and Seghir, M. 2013. *The impact of education on TFP, implications for Senegal*. Paper submitted at UNU-WIDER's conference held in Helsinki, pp1-20, 24-25 June.
- xxi. Nelson, R. and Phelps, E. 1966. *Investment in Humans, Technological Diffusion and Economic Growth*. *American Economic Reviews*. Vol 56, No 2, pp 69: 75.
- xxii. Qutb, R. and El Shennawy, I. 2016. *Exploring the impact of public education expenditure on the economic growth of Egypt*. *The International Research Journal on Finance and Economics*. Issue 146. PP.43-56 .March.
- xxiii. Qutb, R. 2017. *How Education Does At All Levels Influence Total Factors Productivity Growth?*. *The international research journal on finance and economics*, issue 159. pp.58-75. January.
- xxiv. Qutb, R. 2015. *The Evaluation of Public Education Financing Policy in Egypt*. Paper presented at the 17th THEIER international conference on economics and social science, London, UK, pp.13:16.
- xxv. Qutb, R. 2016. *Analyzing the External and Internal Efficiency Considerations in Public Subsidization of Education in Egypt*. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, Vol.7, No.12. June.
- xxvi. Schultz, T. 1961. *Investments in Human Capital*. *American Economic Review*, Vol 51, pp: 1-17.
- xxvii. Tabari, N. and Reza, M. 2012. *Technology and education effects on labor productivity in the agricultural sector in Iran*. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*, VOL 2. NO 4, PP.1265-1272.
- xxviii. *The Human Capital Report*. 2015. *Employment, Skills and Human Capital Global Challenge Insight Report*. *World Economic Forum*, PP.1-319.
- xxix. Todaro, M. 1990. *Economic of Developing World*. second edition, Vikas publishers, New york .
- xxx. Weiss, A. 1995. *Human capital VS. Signaling explanations of wages*. *The journal of economic perspectives*, vol 9, issue 4, pp.133-154.
- xxxi. World Bank. 2009. *Knowledge assessment methodology (KAM)*, cited in *Arab knowledge report*, p.209.